

Online Appendix to “Policy Implications of Losing Credibility: Lessons from Colombia's Post-Pandemic Inflation”

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A. Additional Figures

Figure A. 1 - Impulse response function to a tradable goods cost shock

Note: Response of selected variables to a 100 basis points supply shock. The responses of the endogenous variables are in basis points.

Source: Authors' calculations.

Figure A. 2 - Impulse response function to a demand shock

Note: Response of selected variables to a 100 basis points supply shock. The responses of the endogenous variables are in basis points.

Source: Authors' calculations.

Figure A. 3 - Impulse response function to multiple supply shocks

*Note: Response of selected variables to one, two and three sequential supply shocks of 800 basis points.
Source: Authors' calculations.*

Figure A. 4 - Differences between scenarios with and without endogenous credibility

Note: The results represent the differences between the forecast scenario with endogenous credibility costs and the scenario without credibility costs, both with information up to July 2023 and without additional judgments in the forecast horizon (two years).

Source: Authors' calculations.

B. The Full 4GM-model (Gonzalez et al., 2020)

The model structure can be divided into four main blocks: 1) The IS Curve and potential output growth; 2) the Phillips curves for each CPI basket; 3) the monetary policy rule and definitions of other interest rates; and 4) the uncovered interest parity (UIP) and the process for foreign variables. Shocks are denoted by ε_t and are normally distributed.

1) IS Curve and Potential GDP Growth

The output level in logarithmic terms y_t is defined in terms of a cyclical component \hat{y}_t (output gap) and a trend \bar{y}_t (potential output):

$$y_t = \bar{y}_t + \hat{y}_t \quad (\text{A. 1})$$

$$\bar{y}_t = \bar{y}_{t-1} + \frac{\Delta \bar{y}_t}{4} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$\Delta \bar{y}_t = \rho_{\Delta \bar{y}} \Delta \bar{y}_{t-1} + (1 - \rho_{\Delta \bar{y}}) \left(\Delta \bar{y}_{ss} + \kappa_{\Delta \bar{y}} \left(\Delta \bar{r}p_t^{oil} - \Delta \bar{r}p_{ss}^{oil} \right) \right) + \varepsilon_t^{\Delta \bar{y}} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\hat{y}_t = \beta_1 \hat{y}_{t-1} + \beta_2 \mathbb{E}_t \hat{y}_{t+1} - \beta_\Phi \Phi_t + \beta_{y^*} \hat{y}_t^* + \beta_{\widehat{r}p_t^{oil}} \widehat{r}p_t^{oil} + \eta_t^{\hat{y}} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\Phi_t = \beta_{\hat{r}} \hat{r}_t - (1 - \beta_{\hat{r}}) \hat{z}_t \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\eta_t^{\hat{y}} = \beta_{\eta^{\hat{y}}} \eta_{t-1}^{\hat{y}} + \varepsilon_t^{\hat{y}}, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where Φ_t is the real monetary condition index that captures the effect of the real interest rate gap \hat{r}_t and the real exchange rate gap \hat{z}_t ; \hat{y}_t^* is the foreign output gap; $\widehat{r}p_t^{oil}$ is the real oil price gap; and $\eta_t^{\hat{y}}$ is a demand shock that follows an AR(1) process. Notice that the law of motion of potential growth, $\Delta \bar{y}_t$, depends on its lagged value, the long-term growth rate (steady state), $\Delta \bar{y}_{ss}$, and deviations of the trend growth of the real oil price from its steady state rate, $\left(\Delta \bar{r}p_t^{oil} - \Delta \bar{r}p_{ss}^{oil} \right)$.

2) Phillips Curves and CPI Aggregation

The model considers four CPI baskets j , namely Goods (G), Services (S), Food (F), and Regulated goods (R). Each of them has a Phillips curve of the hybrid form:

$$\pi_t^j = \alpha_{\pi^j} \pi_{t-1}^j + (1 - \alpha_{\pi^j}) \mathbb{E}_t \pi_{t+1}^j + \alpha_{rmc^j}^{rmc^j} rmc_t^j + \varepsilon_t^{\pi^j} \quad \text{for } j = G, S, F, R \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where π_t^j is the annualized quarterly inflation and rmc_t^j is the real marginal cost, given by:

$$rmc_t^j = \begin{cases} \alpha_{\hat{y}}^{rmc^j} \hat{y}_t + (1 - \alpha_{\hat{y}}^{rmc^j}) (\hat{z}_t - \widehat{r}p_t^j) & \text{for } j = G, S \\ \alpha_{\hat{y}}^{rmc^j} \hat{y}_t + (1 - \alpha_{\hat{y}}^{rmc^j}) (\widehat{r}p_t^{F^*} + \hat{z}_t - \widehat{r}p_t^j) & \text{for } j = F \\ \alpha_{\hat{y}}^{rmc^j} \hat{y}_t + (1 - \alpha_{\hat{y}}^{rmc^j}) (\widehat{r}p_t^{oil} + \hat{z}_t - \widehat{r}p_t^j) & \text{for } j = R. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Thus, real marginal costs depend positively on the output gap \hat{y}_t , the real exchange rate gap \hat{z}_t , and each basket relative price $\widehat{r}p_t^j$ gap. In addition, the Phillips curves for food and regulated items include the real relative price gaps of world food prices, $\widehat{r}p_t^{F^*}$, and oil, $\widehat{r}p_t^{oil}$, respectively.

Relative prices and the aggregation of CPI are given by:

$$\widehat{rp}_t^j = rp_t^j - \overline{rp}_t^j \quad \text{for } j = G, S, F, R \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$rp_t^j = p_t^j - p_t \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\overline{rp}_t^j = \overline{rp}_{t-1}^j + \frac{\Delta \overline{rp}_t^j}{4} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$\Delta \overline{rp}_t^j = \rho_{\overline{rp}^j} \Delta \overline{rp}_{t-1}^j + (1 - \rho_{\overline{rp}^j}) \Delta \overline{rp}_{ss}^j + \varepsilon_t^{\Delta \overline{rp}^j} \quad \text{for } j = S, F, R \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$p_t = \omega^G p_t^G + \omega^S p_t^S + \omega^F p_t^F + \omega^R p_t^R + \eta_t \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$0 = \omega^G \widehat{rp}_t^G + \omega^S \widehat{rp}_t^S + \omega^F \widehat{rp}_t^F + \omega^R \widehat{rp}_t^R. \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Thus, relative prices, rp_t^j , are the difference between the price index of sector j , p_t^j , and the consumer price index (CPI), p_t . Each relative price is decomposed in a long-term trend component, \overline{rp}_t^j , and a gap component, \widehat{rp}_t^j , which enter into each corresponding Phillips curve.

3) Monetary Policy Rule and Interest Rates

The monetary policy rate, i_t , is given by a Taylor rule:

$$i_t = \rho_i i_{t-1} + (1 - \rho_i) (\bar{i}_t + \varphi_\pi (\mathbb{E}_t \pi_{t+3}^A - \mathbb{E}_t \bar{\pi}_{t+3}^A) + \varphi_y \hat{y}_t) + \epsilon_t^i, \quad (\text{A.15})$$

where \bar{i}_t is the neutral nominal interest rate and $(\mathbb{E}_t \pi_{t+3}^A - \mathbb{E}_t \bar{\pi}_{t+3}^A)$ captures the deviation of annual inflation expectations from the three periods ahead target. The neutral nominal interest rate is defined by the Fisher equation, $\bar{i}_t = \bar{r} + \pi_{t+1}$, where \bar{r} is the neutral real interest rate is determined by:

$$\Delta \bar{z} = \bar{r} - \bar{r}^* + \overline{prem}_t \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where \bar{r}^* is the neutral real interest rate of the US, \overline{prem}_t is the country's long-term trend risk premium, and $\Delta \bar{z}$ is the long term real depreciation that is in the steady state.

4) *Uncovered Interest Parity (UIP) and Foreign Variables*

One-period ahead expectations of depreciation $\Delta E_t s_{t+1}$ are determined by the UIP:

$$\Delta E_t s_{t+1} = i_t^* - i_t + prem_t + \varepsilon_t^{ls} \quad (\text{A. 17})$$

$$z_t = s_t + p_t^* - p_t \quad (\text{A. 18})$$

$$\hat{z}_t = z_t - \bar{z}_t \quad (\text{A. 19})$$

$$\bar{z}_t = \bar{z}_{t-1} + \frac{\Delta \bar{z}_t}{4} \quad (\text{A. 20})$$

$$\Delta \bar{z}_t = \rho_{\Delta \bar{z}} \Delta \bar{z}_{t-1} + (1 - \rho_{\Delta \bar{z}}) \left(\Delta \bar{z}_{ss} - \nu_{\Delta \bar{z}} \left(\Delta \bar{r}p_t^{oil} - \Delta \bar{r}p_{ss}^{oil} \right) \right) + \varepsilon_t^{\Delta \bar{z}} \quad (\text{A. 21})$$

where Δs_t is the nominal depreciation, i_t^* is the FED funds rate, and $prem_t$ is the risk premium. The real exchange rate, z_t , is decomposed into a long-term component \bar{z}_t and a cyclical component \hat{z}_t .

Finally, the model has a set of exogenous paths for the following foreign variables: the world oil relative price gap, $\widehat{r}p_t^{oil}$, the world food relative price gap, $\widehat{r}p_t^{*F}$, the foreign output gap, \hat{y}_t^* , the foreign headline inflation, π_t^* , the nominal foreign interest rate, i_t^* , the foreign real neutral interest rate, \bar{r}_t^* , the country risk premium, $prem_t$, and the long-term trend country risk premium, \overline{prem}_t . All of them follow an AR(1) process:

$$(\cdot)_t = \rho_{(\cdot)} (\cdot)_{t-1} + (1 - \rho_{(\cdot)}) (\tilde{\cdot}) + \varepsilon_t^{(\cdot)} \quad (\text{A. 22})$$

for $(\cdot) = \{\widehat{r}p_t^{oil}, \widehat{r}p_t^{*F}, \hat{y}_t^*, \pi_t^*, i_t^*, \bar{r}_t^*, prem_t, \overline{prem}_t\}$, where $\rho_{(\cdot)}$ is the persistence and $(1 - \rho_{(\cdot)})$ represents the speed of adjustment towards the corresponding steady-state value $(\tilde{\cdot})$.

Our specification with credibility costs modifies the 4GM model by incorporating equations (**Error! Reference source not found.**) - (**Error! Reference source not found.**) that define our credibility metric depending on the selected loss function, and changes the system of equations (A. 7) by (**Error! Reference**

source not found.) - (Error! Reference source not found.) to incorporate the effects of credibility costs into the Phillips curves.

C. Asymmetry of the Credibility Signal

The response of credibility to deviations of observed inflation from target inflation may not be symmetric. Specifically, credibility might decline more significantly, or only, when observed inflation exceeds the target, whereas it may decrease less severely or remain unaffected when inflation falls below the target. Determining whether the credibility response to inflation deviations is symmetric or asymmetric is an empirical question. This appendix explores the potential for an asymmetric credibility response in Colombia during the period 2003-2023.

To examine this, we consider two asymmetric non-linear functional forms for the credibility signal as alternatives to the symmetric nonlinear form used in Section **Error! Reference source not found.** (Equation (**Error! Reference source not found.**)). In the first alternative (A), we impose asymmetry by assuming that credibility is not affected when the observed inflation is below the target. This specification is shown in Equation (A. 23) below, where the asymmetry assumption is achieved by setting $\omega_5 = 0$:

$$\lambda_t = \begin{cases} e^{(-\omega_1 - \omega_2(\pi_{t-1} - \pi_{t-1}^*)^2)} + \omega_3 + \epsilon_t^{sig} & \text{if } \pi_{t-1} - \pi_{t-1}^* \geq 0 \text{ with } \omega_2 \geq 0 \\ e^{(-\omega_4 - \omega_5(\pi_{t-1} - \pi_{t-1}^*)^2)} + \omega_6 + \epsilon_t^{sig} & \text{if } \pi_{t-1} - \pi_{t-1}^* < 0 \text{ with } \omega_5 = 0. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A. 23})$$

The second alternative (B) is more general, estimating all parameters so that the data determine the potential asymmetry of the credibility response. This specification corresponds to:

$$\lambda_t = \begin{cases} e^{(-\omega_1 - \omega_2(\pi_{t-1} - \pi_{t-1}^*)^2)} + \omega_3 + \epsilon_t^{sig} & \text{if } \pi_{t-1} - \pi_{t-1}^* \geq 0 \text{ with } \omega_2 \leq \omega_3 \\ e^{(-\omega_4 - \omega_5(\pi_{t-1} - \pi_{t-1}^*)^2)} + \omega_6 + \epsilon_t^{sig} & \text{if } \pi_{t-1} - \pi_{t-1}^* < 0 \text{ with } \omega_5 \leq \omega_6. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A. 24})$$

Table A. 1 presents the estimation results for the two alternatives, while Figure A. 5 shows the functional form associated with the two alternative specifications. The data suggest that the credibility response is indeed asymmetric, with credibility declining less when observed inflation is below target than

when it is above target. However, when comparing the estimates of the common parameters for these two alternatives, the differences between the first alternative, where the asymmetry is imposed, and the second alternative, where the data determine the magnitude of the asymmetry, are relatively small.

Table A. 1 - Estimates of asymmetric credibility signals

Parameter	Alternative A	Alternative B
ω_1	$\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-\omega_3}\right)$	$\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-\omega_3}\right)$
ω_2	0.273	0.253
ω_3	0.532	0.529
ω_4	$\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-\omega_6}\right)$	$\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-\omega_6}\right)$
ω_5	0	0.059
ω_6	0.777	0.769

Figure A. 5 - Estimates of asymmetric credibility signals. Functional forms of alternative asymmetric credibility signals

Source: Authors' calculations.

These small differences translate into comparable credibility signals for the two asymmetric alternatives, which, in turn, closely resemble the signal obtained using the symmetric specification in Equation (**Error! Reference source not found.**) (Figure A. 6). This similarity indicates that our estimation of the credibility signal remains robust even when considering asymmetric loss functions.

Figure A. 6 - Credibility signals with different specifications

Source: Authors' calculations.